

Speciation of calcium(II) and magnesium(II) complexes of L-glutamine and succinic acid in ethylene glycol-water mixture

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A pH-metric investigation has been made on the speciation of Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} complexes of glutamine (Gln) and succinic acid (Suc) in varying concentrations (0–60%, v/v) of ethylene glycol-water mixtures at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm^{-3} and temperature 303 K. The active form of ligands is LH. The predominant species detected for Gln complexes are MLH, ML_2H and ML_2 and of Suc are ML_2H and ML_2 . The trend in variation in values of protonation and complex stability constants with dielectric constant is explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

L-Glutamine (Gln) is found on the outer surface of globular proteins and is an important participant in the transfer of nitrogen from skeletal muscle to visceral organs. Inclusion of Gln in the diet increased survival to a bacterial challenge¹. Gln is utilized at a high rate by cells of the immune system² and is required to support optimal lymphocyte proliferation and production of cytokines by lymphocytes and macrophages. Succinic acid (Suc) is involved in citric acid and glyoxalate cycles. For energy production and biosynthesis, many plants and bacteria convert two-carbon acetyl units into four-carbon succinate units in glyoxalate cycle. Suc can be used³ for manufacture of medicaments or nutritional supplements effective for treating of insulin resistance in mammals.

Ethylene glycol (EG) is a protophilic dipolar protic solvent⁴ and acts as a structure-former. EG is more acidic than water due to electron-withdrawing effect of CH_2 groups. Ethylene glycol offers several advantages as solvent in titration of weak bases. Hence, the speciation studies of Gln and Suc with Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} in EG-water mixtures have been reported in this paper.

Results and Discussion

Modeling of equilibria :

Alkalimetric titration curves in EG-water mixtures reveal that the acidobasic equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid are active in the pH ranges 1.5–9.5 and 3.0–6.0, respectively. The best-fit models containing the protonation constants and statistical parameters are given in Table 1.

Models containing various number and combination of complex species of Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} with L-glutamine and succinic acid are generated using an expert system package

CEES⁵. The finally refined model for Gln complexes contains ML_2 , MLH, ML_2H and that for Suc complexes contains ML_2 and ML_2H . A model containing MLH, ML_2 and ML_2H for Suc is rejected because of low percentage (<10%) of MLH species. The final models are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Best-fit chemical models of acido-basic equilibria in EG-water mixtures

EG % (v/v)	$\log \beta_1$ (SD)	$\log \beta_2$ (SD)	$\log \beta_1$ (SD)	$\log \beta_2$ (SD)
	L-Glutamine pH range : 1.5–11.0		Succinic acid pH range : 3.0–7.0	
00.0	9.27 (1)	11.66 (2)	5.43 (1)	9.46 (1)
10.0	8.91 (2)	11.46 (2)	5.35 (5)	9.49 (7)
20.0	8.86 (7)	11.23 (9)	5.42 (4)	9.60 (5)
30.0	9.31 (1)	11.81 (1)	5.58 (5)	9.86 (6)
40.0	9.01 (2)	11.54 (2)	5.79 (8)	10.22 (7)
50.0	9.65 (5)	12.45 (4)	6.19 (8)	10.89 (1)
60.0	9.75 (6)	12.72 (6)	6.42 (8)	11.36 (1)

Solute-solvent interactions :

The linear variation of stepwise protonation constants of Gln and Suc and $\log K$ values of Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} complexes of Gln and Suc in EG-water with $1/D$ (where D is dielectric constant of the medium) indicates that electrostatic forces are dominating the equilibrium process under the present experimental conditions.

Distribution diagrams :

L-Glutamine has three functional groups (amino, carboxyl and amido) but only amino and carboxyl groups can

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagrams in 40% EG-water mixture : (A) Ca^{II}-Gln (B) Mg^{II}-Gln. (C) Ca^{II}-Suc, (D) Mg^{III}-Suc.

associate with protons. Succinic acid has two carboxyl groups and both are protonated. Distribution plots of various forms of ligands indicate the existence of LH₂⁺, LH and L⁻ for Gln and LH₂, LH⁻, and L²⁻ for Suc⁶. The zwitterionic form (LH) of Gln is present to an extent of 90% in the pH range 2.5–8.5. The [LH₂] and [LH⁻] of Suc increase with increased EG content and the maximum concentration of LH⁻ is shifted to higher pH. These two observations indicate the stabilization of the two species with increased concentration of EG.

The present study is confined to the pH range 1.8–10.5 for Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} complexes of Gln. In this pH range, the ligand is present in the form of LH₂⁺, LH and L⁻. Hence, the plausible metal-ligand species are MLH, ML₂H and ML₂ which are confirmed by MINQUAD75⁷. The pH range of study for Suc complexes is 3.0–7.0, where the active forms of Suc are LH₂ and LH⁻. The species confirmed in the pH range are ML₂ and ML₂H. The formation equilibria can be represented as follows :

The formation of MLH in the first equilibrium for Suc is found to be insignificant as the (MLH) is less than 10%. The variation of species concentration with pH is shown in Fig. 1 for some typical systems. In glutamine speciation, concentration of free metal (FM) decreases and ML₂H increases with increasing concentration of EG. In succinate complexes [ML₂] and [ML₂H] are almost unaltered. Another notable observation is that the free metal ion concentration is negligible in the presence of Gln, whereas it is considerably high in the presence of succinic acid, which indicates that Gln is a stronger complexing agent than Suc.

Biological relevance of present study :

The presence of ethylene glycol in aqueous solution considerably decreases the dielectric constant and these solutions are expected to mimic the physiological condi-

tions where the concept of the equivalent solution dielectric constant⁸ for protein cavities is applicable. The present study is useful to understand (i) the role played by the active site cavities in biological molecules, (ii) the type of complex formed by the metal ion, and (iii) the bonding behavior of the protein residues with the metal ion.

Table 2. Best-fit chemical models of Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} complexes of glutamine and succinic acid in EG-water mixtures

EG % (v/v)	log β _{mH} (SD)			log β _{mH} (SD)	
	120	111	121	120	121
	Ca ^{II} -glutamine :			Ca ^{II} -succinic acid :	
	pH range :			pH range :	
	1.8-10.5			3.0-7.0	
00.0	2.81 (4)	10.14(9)	11.41 (4)	3.34 (4)	8.21 (4)
10.0	2.94 (4)	10.34(9)	11.52 (3)	3.49 (7)	8.73 (2)
20.0	3.31 (2)	10.55(5)	12.08 (3)	3.61 (4)	9.50 (9)
30.0	3.43 (6)	11.76 (4)	Rej.	3.58 (4)	9.50 (5)
40.0	3.40 (7)	10.32(8)	12.57 (1)	3.49 (4)	9.82 (8)
50.0	3.69 (1)	11.07(2)	13.93 (1)	3.70 (96)	10.38(8)
60.0	3.57 (3)	11.53 (2)	14.10(1)	3.41 (9)	10.43 (8)
	Mg ^{II} -glutamine :			Mg ^{II} -succinic acid :	
	pH range :			pH range :	
	1.8-10.5			3.0-7.0	
00.0	3.40 (4)	10.82 (2)	11.56 (3)	2.71 (6)	9.43 (8)
10.0	3.61 (5)	10.76 (6)	11.91 (7)	3.23 (9)	9.51 (7)
20.0	3.66 (3)	11.21 (4)	12.38 (3)	3.17 (6)	9.95 (8)
30.0	Rej.	11.48 (6)	Raj.	3.21 (8)	9.37 (8)
40.0	3.94 (3)	11.54 (2)	13.49 (4)	3.14 (7)	9.74 (6)
50.0	4.48 (2)	11.88 (3)	14.41 (2)	3.14 (8)	10.26 (8)
60.0	3.43 (3)	10.52 (7)	13.83 (8)	3.45 (4)	10.42 (9)

Experimental

Solution of L-glutamine, succinic acid, calcium(II) and magnesium(II) chlorides (E. Merck) were prepared in triple-distilled water. A 99.5% pure ethylene glycol (E. Merck) was used. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentration, the data were subjected to ANOVA. The strength of alkali was determined using the Gran plot method⁹.

The titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations (10–60%, v/v) of EG in water main-

taining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ with NaCl at 303.0 ± 0.1 K using a Systronic 335 pH meter. The glass electrode was equilibrated in EG-water mixture containing inert electrolyte. The correction factor (log *F*), to correct the pH meter dial readings, was determined using SCPHD program¹⁰. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 3 and 1 : 5) of metal-to-ligand were carried out with 0.4 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere¹¹.

The approximate complex stability constants were calculated with the computer program SCPHD. Following some heuristics¹² in the refinement of the stability constants, the best-fit chemical models for each system were arrived at using a computer program MINQUAD75.

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